

THE NEED TO DEVELOP PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES BASED ON A CREATIVE-PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH

Abdurakhmanov Dilmurod Akramaliyevych

Independent researcher of the Kokan State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of developing professional competence in future pedagogues based on a creative-pedagogical approach, the technological system of developing professional competence in future pedagogues based on a creative-pedagogical approach, and the effectiveness of developing professional competence in future pedagogues based on a creative-pedagogical approach. Also, components of professional competence development in future pedagogues based on the creative-pedagogical approach were analyzed.

Key words: future pedagogue, creative-pedagogical, competence, educational, reproductive, retrospective, competence, professional competence, creative-pedagogical approach, technological system, theoretical-methodological basis.

INTRODUCTION. In the explanatory dictionary of the science of pedagogy, the term "profession" is explained as follows: "As a result of special training and work experience, a profession acquires a set of theoretical knowledge, practical skills and qualifications for the implementation of professional activities in a certain field, which is defined as physical ability, mental ability and is a type of human activity that ensures legal rights".

The issues related to the choice of a profession and the formation of professional activity are covered in the research works of several pedagogic scientists. For example: Professor J. Khasanboyev pays attention to professional activity in the training of future specialists and defines professional activity as follows: -Professional function - belongs to the graduate of the relevant educational institutions, and is able to perform activities in the field occupied by the person in life. , is the activity of mastering knowledge within the scope of one's profession and being able to apply it in practice without deviation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Preparation for professional activity, social-philosophical and pedagogical-psychological foundations of professional competence development in future pedagogues based on a creative-pedagogical approach Wilson, J. Kim, Angela Stoff, Benjamin Bloom, Brian Cole, Drapeau Patty, Jaslin Holberg, Merriembar Jeron, O.A. Kolesnik . It

was researched in the scientific research of such scientists as Mahkamov, O.Musurmonova, S.Nishonova, V.Slastenin, D.Roziyeva, B.Khodjayev, Sh.Sharipov, Sh.Shodmonova, Y.Shiyanov, N.Egamberdiyeva, M.Kuronov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Professional competence is used in relation to the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of professional activities and their practical application at a high level. Professional competence implies not only the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills, but also the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of specialized knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it and being able to use it in one's work.

Professor M. Ochilov in his work "Teacher's Etiquette" gives the opinion that "such ethics, which include moral norms and requirements for people engaged in a certain field of activity, is called professional (professional) ethics." The scientist emphasizes the need to cultivate high moral qualities in the preparation of future teachers for professional activities.

Pedagogical scientist A. Kholikov based on the essence of the teaching profession in his research gives the opinion that "Pedagogical profession is a stable system of socially important qualities that act as a perfect human being."

In his research, scientist B.K. Rakhimov studied the professional and cultural attitudes of future teachers. According to him: "Professional cultural relations are the main means of achieving interpersonal, positive relations, fulfills their role and serves to improve personal activity."

For example, in the research of the researcher G. Boymurodov, he emphasizes "the effect of preparation for the pedagogical profession, deepening the ability to master more subjects and see the results in practice." Based on the research of the above scientists, it is known that the preparation of future specialists for their professional activities is a complex and multifaceted process. Areas that justify the content of professional activity:

1. Profession - educational pedagogy; (R.Kh. Djorayev, S.T. Turgunov)
2. Professional knowledge (Kh. Torakulov, J. Khasanboyev, N. Muslimov, F. Yuzlikayev)
3. Profession-oriented teaching technology (N. Saidakhmedov, R. Eshmukhamedov, S. Bozorova, O. Haydarova)
4. Professional culture (N. Egamberdiyeva, B. Rakhimov, Sh. Shodmonova)
5. Professional skills and design (R.Kh. Dzhorayev, S.T. Turgunov)

6. Professional experience, professional education, field of professional activity, professional function, the content and essence of the concepts defined by the rules in the field of the profession belong to the work of the scientists named above.

B. Rakhimov, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, created a system of professional cultural relations in scientific research, substantiated the essence of its application in pedagogical practice and expressed the following opinions: "Today's student, especially the teacher, has a harmony of both relations, that is, professional and cultural relations. It is necessary for social life to be consistent and consistent.

In his doctoral thesis, Professor N. Muslimov gives his opinion on the organization of the professional activity of specialists and expresses the following points: "The presence of professional qualities in a person is expressed through the indicator of his formation as a specialist. ... The process of organizing the professional activity of a specialist is carried out sequentially in certain stages."

S. Bozorova, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, in her monograph "Professionally oriented teaching technology in higher education" defines vocationally oriented teaching technology as follows: technology that forms personal qualities, as well as skills and competencies that ensure the fulfillment of functional obligations according to the task".

In the process of professional self-management in modern socio-economic conditions, the most complete psychological forms of the individual's professional development, the development characteristics of professional competence were studied by E.F. Zeyer. He assesses professional competence as one of the main components of the structure of professional activity. It also represents the orientation of the person, professionally important qualities, professionally important psychophysiological characteristics.

Competence approach, formation of all-round competence in human activity is considered the main condition of modern society and education. This requirement is directly related to the future activities of future teachers. Today, the main direction of the renewal of world education is to be able to see the world, life, pedagogical activities in a systematic way through an active approach in the educational process, to perform systematic activities in it, and to form the experience of being able to solve new problems and tasks. .

Based on the above points, we present our author's tariff for professional competence: Professional competence has an integral character. It is the level of

ability and readiness to solve professional problems and professional tasks in the situations that arise in the course of professional activity, and it implies the use of knowledge, skills, competence, professional and life experience, values and culture.

Professional competence is evident in the following cases:

- in complex processes;
- performing unclear tasks;
- using conflicting information;
- a specialist who has acquired professional competence in being able to come up with an action plan in an unexpected situation:
 - constantly enriches his knowledge;
 - learns new information;
 - deeply understands the requirements of the era;
 - searches for new knowledge, processes them and uses them effectively in his practical work.

Below, the essence of the qualities reflected on the basis of professional competence will be briefly explained. 1. Ijtimoiy kompetentlik – ijtimoiy munosabatlarda faollik ko'rsatish ko'nikma, malakalariga yegalik, pedagogik faoliyat da subyektlar bilan muloqotga kirisha olish.

2. Special competence - preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activities, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of activity results, consistent development of BKM, based on this competence psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence noticeable. They contain the following content:

- psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, to be able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in time;
- methodical competence - methodically rational organization of the pedagogical process, correct determination of the forms of educational or educational activities, ability to choose methods and tools in accordance with the purpose, ability to effectively use methods, successful use of tools;
- informational competence - searching, collecting, sorting, processing necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment and using it purposefully, appropriately, effectively;
- creative competence - critical and creative approach to pedagogical activity, ability to demonstrate one's own creative skills;

- innovative competence - putting forward new ideas on improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and successfully implementing them into practice;

- communicative competence - being able to communicate sincerely with all participants of the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, to have a positive influence on them.

3. Personal competence - consistently achieving professional growth, increasing the level of competence, demonstrating one's internal capabilities in professional activity.

4. Technological competence - mastering advanced technologies that enrich professional and pedagogical BKM, being able to use modern tools, techniques and technologies.

In Great Britain, the concept of "competence" is used in different ways. In addition, competencies are divided into key skills, subject skills, and base skills.

The following three competencies are distinguished among the main competencies: working with numbers; communicative; information Technology. Broader among them: independent education and self-presentation; work in groups; problem solving.

CONCLUSION. Activity is an active manifestation of personality in behavior, and it is characterized as the ability to develop professional competencies that can be mastered by a person in any necessary situation. The components of professional competences are considered as minimal and sufficiently private constructions that meet the standards of competence for any specialty and determine the professional competence of a specialist. Based on the private construction of professional skills, the main qualities necessary for a qualified specialist are developed. In the conditions of development of professional competence, it is possible to form various parts and types of its content.

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